

Research data repositories and what to consider when choosing one for deposit

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Abstract

The main purpose of the present chapter is to provide practical guidance with regard to selecting a suitable data repository for research data. The chapter might be helpful for researchers, librarians, and research support staff. Choosing a research data repository (RDR) that is appropriate for research data can be challenging and may be influenced by various factors such as the specific character of the data, requirements imposed on the researchers by third parties, e.g. a funding agency or publisher. Therefore, different types of repositories are briefly characterized in recognition of the fact that scientific disciplines or research communities have different requirements for their data management - sometimes due to the characteristics of their data, and to some extent due to the specific academic culture that has evolved. Further, directories of data repositories are presented that may be helpful in finding an appropriate place for research data storage and/or data publication. Next, data policy frameworks of some scientific journal publishers are summarized pointing to a broad spectrum of potential data sharing requirements when submitting to a journal. The final section discusses some important issues and questions to be considered in the repository selection process.

Keywords: research data, research data repository, data archive, data policy, scholarly journal, journal publisher

Abstract (in German)

Das vorliegende Kapitel soll Forschern, Bibliothekaren und Mitarbeitenden von Forschungseinrichtungen als praktische Orientierungshilfe zur Auswahl eines Datenrepositoriums dienen. Die Wahl oder Empfehlung eines für Forschungsdaten geeigneten Repositoriums (RDR) kann eine Herausforderung sein und von verschiedenen Faktoren beeinflusst werden, wie z. B. dem spezifischen Charakter der Daten, oder den Anforderungen, die den Forschern von Dritten, z. B. einer Förderinstitution oder einem Verlag, auferlegt werden. Zuerst werden verschiedene Arten von Repositorien kurz charakterisiert, um der Tatsache Rechnung zu tragen, dass wissenschaftliche Disziplinen oder Forschungsgemeinschaften unterschiedliche Anforderungen an ihr Datenmanagement stellen - manchmal aufgrund der Merkmale ihrer Daten und in gewissem Maße auch aufgrund der spezifischen akademischen Kultur, die sich entwickelt hat. Außerdem werden einige Verzeichnisse von Datenrepositorien vorgestellt, die bei der Suche nach einem geeigneten Ort für die Speicherung und/oder Veröffentlichung von Forschungsdaten hilfreich sein können. Anschließend werden am Beispiel einiger großer wissenschaftlicher Zeitschriftenverlage Rahmen-Datenrichtlinien zusammenfassend vorgestellt. Die abschließende Zusammenfassung liefert Überlegungen, die zur Auswahl eines geeigneten Datenrepositoriums von Bedeutung sind und formuliert Fragen, die von den jeweiligen Datenautoren:innen zuvor beantwortet werden sollten.

Schlagwörter: Forschungsdaten, Datenrepositorium, Daten teilen, Datenpolitik, Forschungspublikation, Zeitschriftenverlag

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1. Introduction

In recent years, depositing datasets associated with published research has become more common. Amongst other factors, such as proper research data management as an element of Good Scientific Practice (cf. DFG, ÖAWI and others), this is due to an increase in journals requiring data sharing¹. It has been evidenced that journal-based data archiving policies could be very effective in ensuring that research data are available to the scientific community to enable reuse and reproducibility of results, especially when journals require that a data accessibility statement to be provided in the published paper². Key contributions towards increasing availability and accessibility of research data have been the OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding³ as well as the formulation of the FAIR Data principles⁴. In the case of publicly funded research projects (e.g. EU H2020 projects, FWF-funded projects), the funding bodies are increasingly demanding that the associated research data be stored in a data repository and be openly accessible as far as possible (ERC, H2020, FWF, etc.).

The first objective of this chapter is to present the reader different types of research data repositories, being one of the ways to publish and share research, and second, to provide some guidance when selecting a repository for the data deposit. The chapter primarily aims at staff generally offering research services or advising researchers on data repositories, but it may also serve as a helpful source of information for researchers themselves.

In the next section (Section 2), by including definitions concerning data and data repositories, the different types of RDR are described in more detail. Additionally, examples of some RDR are given. Where available, links to the actual websites or related content is provided. However, the development of the landscape of RDR is dynamic and finding an appropriate data repository may be a daunting task. The emerging of directories of research data repositories may be helpful for finding a suitable place to deposit research data (Section 3). Data (sharing) policies and recommendations on data deposits by publishers and research funders are another important aspect in the publishing process. Hence, in Section 4, some examples from important publishers of scholarly journals are presented. In the context of the previous chapters, section 5 summarizes and considers issues of choosing a proper repository for data deposit.

2. Types and characteristics of research data repositories (RDR)

Data repositories not only serve as a storage infrastructure but may also help make a researcher's research data more discoverable, accessible, and hence leading to potential reuse and increased citation of scientific work. Furthermore, it may enable reproducibility of results, making research outcomes more transparent. There is also evidence for a statistically well-supported

¹ Resnik et al. (2019)

² Vines et al. (2013 and 2020)

³ OECD (2007)

⁴ Wilkinson et al. (2016)

citation benefit from open data⁵. Research tradition or discipline requirements imposed by publisher and funders, as well as institutional or national policies, may influence if, how and where researchers archive or publish the data that underlie their published research in dedicated repositories. There exist different types of RDR. Looking at the scope of research areas a repository covers, one can distinguish between two core types of data repositories: discipline-specific RDRs and general-purpose (or generic) RDRs. Following the US Geological Survey⁶, throughout this contribution, the terms “*data repository*” and “*data archive*”⁷ will be used synonymously. The same will apply for the term “*research data repository*” (RDR) and “*research data archive*”.

A professionally operated data repository should always be the first choice for depositing research datasets. There, the data is published in a thematically appropriate ecosystem, such repositories are recognized in their respective discipline, and the visibility of the data is high. A domain- or discipline-specific repository is likely a good choice for data that can be publicly shared⁸. If there is no suitable repository available or the requirements for the datasets cannot be met by a generic repository, services such as for example Zenodo⁹ can be used as a second step¹⁰. If these services are not an option, e.g. because the amount of data is too large, or external storage is not possible for legal reasons, institutional research data repositories are a good place to publish. For the institution (and its researchers), having its own repository, this may have several advantages. By having control over the published datasets, one can specify the quality of the metadata and ensure that the data remain in-house. The publication process can also be designed and controlled independently of third parties. It also increases the visibility of the institution and improves the overview of the published datasets of an institution. A general discussion and good overview on these subjects can be found in some recently published books¹¹.

There are various options available for the storage of research data. It can be stored in data archives or data repositories. An important step is to find out whether your institution operates such a platform (an institutional data archive or repository) or collaborates with a data centre where it may be compulsory to store your data. If this is not the case, it is advisable, particularly with a view to allowing other researchers to reuse your data, to find out whether any subject-specific repositories exist for your particular discipline where your data can be stored. Directories of repositories are useful tools for finding a suitable repository as for example

⁵ Piwowar and Vision (2013)

⁶ U.S. Geological Survey (2022)

⁷ From different perspectives, the two terms may represent different concepts. Further details will not be discussed as it is beyond the scope of this chapter. The USGS approach will be followed here. For more details, see the terms archive and repository in the online dictionary of the Society of American Archivists (2022) or the German RDM information platform [forschungsdaten.info](https://www.forschungsdaten.info/praxis-kompakt/glossar) (<https://www.forschungsdaten.info/praxis-kompakt/glossar>)

⁸ Whyte (2015)

⁹ <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

¹⁰ see for example, the data repository guidance for the Journal Scientific Data (available at: <https://www.nature.com/sdata/policies/repositories> last accessed 31-08-2022)

¹¹ Cox and Verbaan (2018) and Corti et al. (2020)

re3data¹², which currently lists more than 2600 repositories (see Section 3 for more details). Repositories may offer open access to data while others offer restricted access to the data (i.e. only metadata can be accessed; or embargo on a dataset) or no access rights at all¹³.

2.1 Research data

Research data are generated by various methods - depending on the research question. Data used or created within a research project may be *primary data* generated in the course of source research, experiments, measurements, interviews, surveys or polls. If data have been collected or produced by others than the author(s) and are already available (e.g. census data), then they are termed *secondary data*. Depending on the research design, datasets may consist of both. This research data usually form the basis for scientific publications. Beside the different perspectives and concepts what data generally is¹⁴, quite a lot of different definitions of *research data* can be found in the literature¹⁵. The definition by the German Research Foundation¹⁶, and the one by the Office of Management and Budget at the US Whitehouse (2020)¹⁷ exemplifies the diversity of viewpoints on research data. The OECD¹⁸ has defined research data “as factual records (numerical scores, textual records, images and sounds) used as primary sources for scientific research, and that are commonly accepted in the scientific community as necessary to validate research findings. ...”. For simplicity the term *research data* is referred to (digital) data that, depending on the subject context¹⁹, are the *subject* of a research process, and are *generated during* a research process *or are its result*.

2.2 Research data repository (RDR)

Generally, a research data repository (or data archive) can be characterized as technical infrastructure and the final destination of research data that are determined to be stored for the long term. Structure and characteristics of scientific data – the content of an RDR – differ greatly in the respective research disciplines. Legal regulations may also influence the decision if, where and how to archive research data. Other reasons for the different requirements for data management are the diversity of research traditions and publication cultures that have developed over time in the numerous disciplines. In simple terms, a research data repository represents an institutionalized storage location for digital research data. If you look more closely, it is not that simple, and there exist definitions that are more detailed. For example, a

¹² <http://www.re3data.org/>

¹³ re3data.org (2020)

¹⁴ Kitchin (2021)

¹⁵ Cox and Verbaan (2018), pp. 19

¹⁶ DFG (2009), p.2

¹⁷ Office of Management and Budget [=OMB] (2020); see also https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/legacy_drupal_files/omb/circulars/A110/2cfr215-0.pdf and for further details on OMB's functions within the US Government, see <https://www.whitehouse.gov/omb/>

¹⁸ OECD (2007), p. 13

¹⁹ Kindling and Schirmbacher (2013), p. 130

data archive can be termed as the organizational unit that responsibly takes on the task of data management within a defined frame of reference, and a data repository as the realization of a data storage facility in that data archive²⁰.

Types of research data repositories

Selecting a research data repository that is appropriate for the data in question can be quite challenging and sometimes depends on very specific requirements that may arise from the data itself, but also from requirements imposed on the researcher by third parties, like publishers or funders (see Section 4 below for data policy issues). Data repositories can be distinguished along different attributes: the disciplinary context of data, functional criteria, organizational embedding, how it is operated (commercial/non-commercial) and special purposes. Hence, a certain repository may fall into more than one of the below mentioned categories. Nevertheless, one can distinguish the following (non-disjoint) types of data repositories²¹:

- (i) *Domain-specific* research data repositories (dedicated to a certain discipline, or a certain research field, hence sometimes called subject-repository),
- (ii) *Generic data repositories* usually open for all kind of research data (for example Zenodo),
- (iii) *Institutional (data) repositories* (e.g. operated by a university²²), and
- (iv) *Software repositories* (e.g. Github, especially for depositing software, or software projects)
- (v) *Commercially operated repositories*, usually operated by a profit-oriented company (or part of it; e.g. Figshare)

It should be noted, that repositories of type (i), (ii), and (iv) can also be commercially oriented (i.e. falling into category (iv)). In general, the types of data repositories do not represent disjoint types or classes. Therefore, in Table 1 some typical characteristics of research data repositories are presented. Software repositories are somewhat different in comparison to the classical research data archives for several reasons. They are rather generic in their nature, hence usually not focused on special scientific disciplines. Another characteristic is the availability of services for private or commercial projects as well as researcher projects. The initial or further development of software is a process that may take months or years, and software may be updated over time by releasing new versions. In summary, this indicates a significant difference in use compared to the classic research data repository, where the archived data has usually reached a final state. A recent short overview on software repositories provides some factors to be considered in the selection process²³. It should be noted that the RDR landscape is dynamic in its nature: for example, a repository may be subject to changes in its business model or extending the scope of the data to be archived. Therefore, features listed in the table below may

²⁰ Ludwig and Enke (2013), p. 47-48

²¹ see for example, Baker and Duerr (2017), pp. 141, for more details

²² for example, GAMS, which is the Humanities' Asset Management System of the University of Graz and contains not only research data <https://gams.uni-graz.at/archive/objects/context:gams/methods/sdef:Context/get?mode=about> (Stigler and Steiner 2018)

²³ Hong (2020)

be not exclusively apply to only one type of repository. In the author's recent experience, researchers are sometimes looking for a quick fix for their data deposit, and therefore do not give equal importance to all the options listed below, but rather try to meet the minimum requirements set by funders or publishers.

Table 1: Data Repository types²⁴: Usual characteristics, potential advantages and disadvantages. Features may not be available for all repositories listed in the example column, but rather indicate usual core features that can be expected for this class of repositories.

Repository type	Description of features typically present/expected		Examples
	Potential advantages	Potential problems or shortcomings	
Domain specific digital repositories/data archives (disciplinary repositories)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ meeting data quality standards ▪ PID ▪ long-term preservation ▪ data catalogues for discovery ▪ licensing arrangements ▪ promotion of data ▪ monitoring secondary use of data ▪ management of access to data ▪ management of user requests on behalf of data owner ▪ enhanced consulting services for data depositors ▪ training offers ▪ data curation services ▪ may provide self-deposit for partner institutions ▪ additional tools and services along the research cycle²⁵ ▪ usually highly acknowledged by funders' policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ may accept only specific data that are typical for the respective research domain ▪ (possibly) costs involved in depositing data or curation services ▪ data depositing process may be a little more involved, i.e. time and effort of the depositing process may be an entry barrier for potential submitters 	UKDA (UK Data Archive) ²⁶ AUSSDA (Austrian Social Science Data Archive) ²⁷ DARIAH-DE (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) ²⁸ CESSDA (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives) ²⁹ ICPSR (Inter-University Consortium for Political and Social Research) ³⁰

²⁴ Parts of the table have been adopted from Haaker and Corti (2020), pp. 276-277

²⁵ See, for example, <https://de.dariah.eu/web/guest/dienste-und-werkzeuge> (accessed 23-12-2022)

²⁶ <https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/> (UK's largest digital collection of social sciences and population research data)

²⁷ <https://aussda.at/>

²⁸ <https://de.dariah.eu/en/dariah-de-in-kurze> or <https://de.dariah.eu/en/home>

²⁹ <https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/> As a consortium CESSDA rather acts as a data-catalogue

³⁰ <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/pages/>

<p>Special purpose repositories / data community driven repositories</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ characteristics similar to those of domain specific repositories ▪ homogeneous data and data ingest process³¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ for smaller research communities, operating their own data repository may not be commensurate with the effort required 	<p>BMRB (Biological Magnetic Resonance Data Bank)³²</p> <p>wwPDB³³</p> <p>x-econ.org³⁴ (focus on experimental economics data)</p>
<p>Institutional digital repositories³⁵</p> <p>(For more examples, use a query at re3data.org³⁶)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accepting usually all data collections created by their staff ▪ Deposit usually at no cost to staff ▪ Locality of data (may be important in case e.g. of highly sensitive data) ▪ Visibility via institutional channels ▪ Suitable for small datasets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Probably lacking data management and diversity of metadata profiles to manage different disciplinary data ▪ Limited data curation in smaller institutions due to limited personnel resources or lack of expertise ▪ Number of datasets sometimes rather small compared to efforts required to run this service 	<p>GAMS (Humanities Asset Management System)³⁷</p> <p>IST Austria (Institute of Science and Technology – Austria)</p> <p>PHAIDRA³⁸ (Permanent Hosting, Archiving and Indexing of Digital Resources and Assets)</p>
<p>Generic digital repository</p> <p>(ranging from general purpose³⁹ to cross-disciplinary data repositories)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accept a wide range of data types ▪ Suitable for cross-disciplinary data ▪ Suitable for smaller datasets ▪ Data owner usually has controls publishing and access of dataset 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No or less editorial control of quality of the data or metadata ▪ No or limited data curation services ▪ limited metadata profiles ▪ Location of physical storage of data may be legally relevant⁴⁰ 	<p>Zenodo (non-profit)</p> <p>Figshare (commercial)</p> <p>Harvard dataverse (non-profit, based on the dataverse project⁴¹)</p> <p>Dryad⁴²</p>

³¹ This means data usually the data that are to be deposited in such repositories are homogeneous in terms of their characteristics, contents and structure, which is advantageous to the ingest process.

³² <https://bmr.io/>

³³ <https://www.wwpdb.org/>

³⁴ A repository on experimental economics, since 2018: <https://x-econ.org/xecon/#!AGB>

³⁵ Operated by a research institution and usually only available for faculty members of the entire institution or projects where at least one project member must be affiliated with the institution.

³⁶ Example query at re3data.org using “European Union” AND “institutional” as filter terms:

<https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&types%5B%5D=institutional&countries%5B%5D=EEC>

³⁷ GAMS is the Humanities’ Asset Management System of the University of Graz and contains not only research data but also other digital objects <https://gams.uni-graz.at/archive/objects/context:gams/methods/sdef:Context/get?mode=about>; (see Stigler and Steiner 2018, for more details on GAMS)

³⁸ <https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/>

³⁹ Generalist repositories accept data regardless of data type, format, content, or disciplinary focus

⁴⁰ For example, a research institution does not allow data deposits where the physical cloud-storage is located in the US.

⁴¹ See for more details on the project King (2007)

⁴² https://datadryad.org/stash/our_mission

			RADAR ⁴³ (Research Data Repository)
Software repositories⁴⁴	<i>Exemplary characteristics⁴⁵:</i> Available for private, commercial and research projects Usually for open-source licensed projects Some allowing for data hosting (e.g. git-annex for very large data files) Depersonalization of services Different version control systems Certain services are fee-based Developer- vs. project-focused environments		Github (a more developer focused environment) Bitbucket Sourceforge CRAN ⁴⁶ (Comprehensive R Archive Network)

A further distinction can be made between *special purpose repositories* and *disciplinary repositories*. While latter have their emphasis on research data (and the related research papers) on a certain scientific discipline or sub discipline as a whole, the former have their focus on a specific topic or the type of data collected in these repositories is very narrow and homogeneous in its structure. Especially, in the STEM-fields⁴⁷ the emergence of such repositories can be facilitated by the formation and longer-term existence of so-called *data communities* that focus on lively data exchange or sharing⁴⁸. In a blogpost⁴⁹ at Springer Nature, Matthews (2022) states: “Each community repository is built around a specific data type, and this data-specificity yields several advantages”, this term refers to the more common terms subject-specific or domain-specific repository. Here are two examples for special purpose archives: First, the Biological Magnetic Resonance Databank⁵⁰ which is a special purpose repository for experimental and derived data gathered from nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopic studies of biological molecules⁵¹. Second, the Protein Data Bank⁵² archive (PDB) has served as the single repository of information about the 3D structures of proteins, nucleic acids, and complex assemblies. The Worldwide PDB (wwPDB) organization manages the PDB archive and ensures that the PDB is freely and publicly available to the global community⁵³. At the same time, these two repositories serve a highly specialized data community.

⁴³ <https://www.radar-service.eu/en>; for details, see Potterat et al. (2014) and Kraft et al. (2016) and <https://radar.products.fiz-karlsruhe.de/en/radarabout/ueber-radar>

⁴⁴ <https://www.software.ac.uk/choosing-repository-your-software-project>

⁴⁵ (the +/- descriptions do not apply for SW-repositories)

⁴⁶ <https://cran.r-project.org/>

⁴⁷ Abbr. for *Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics*

⁴⁸ Cooper and Springer (2019)

⁴⁹ Matthews (2022)

⁵⁰ BMRB (<https://bmr.io/>) is a special purpose repository for experimental and derived data gathered from nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopic studies of biological molecules.

⁵¹ Ulrich et al. (2007)

⁵² <https://www.wwpdb.org>

⁵³ wwPDB consortium (2018)

3. Directories of RDR – or where to search for an appropriate repository

Directories of repositories are internet portals hosted by different organizations and bodies and provide information about available repositories and related information. Based on the respective functionalities this information can be discovered by browsing and searching capabilities. The scope of searchable content thereby may vary quite a lot. In addition, repository descriptions may differ in comprehensiveness and detail among the registries. In the following, examples of some the most prominent directories are provided:

- *re3data.org*⁵⁴ is by far the most comprehensive registry of RDRs. Since 2021 it provides information about more than 2600 data repositories⁵⁵ from different academic disciplines all over the world⁵⁶ and has a broad set of functions and features⁵⁷. It uses an icon-system for visually indicating important features of a repository⁵⁸. See Table 2 for example entries in this registry.
- *OpenDOAR* (since 2005)⁵⁹ is a quality-assured, global directory of Open Access Repositories. It is not limited to data repositories. One can search and browse through thousands of registered repositories based on a range of features, such as location, software or type of material held.
- *FAIRsharing*⁶⁰ provides curated information on data repositories, data and metadata standards, and data policies⁶¹.
- *Datacite's Repository Finder*⁶² can help to find an appropriate repository to deposit research data. The tool is hosted by DataCite⁶³ and queries the re3data registry. It further provides two predefined queries via the re3data registry to get a list of RDR that meet the criteria of the Enabling FAIR Data Project and the FAIRsFAIR Project⁶⁴. Actually, DataCite has further developed its search tool: the „Repository Search“-Feature replaces the previous tool and merges metadata from re3data and DataCite in one place⁶⁵.
- *Core Trust Seal*⁶⁶ provides a (searchable) list of data repositories that are certified by at least one of the following data service providers: WDS (World Data Systems)⁶⁷, DSA

⁵⁴ <http://re3data.org/>; online since 2012

⁵⁵ <https://blogs.tib.eu/wp/dini-ag-blog/2021/05/27/re3data-literaturanalyse/>

⁵⁶ Strecker and Weisweiler (2021), <https://blogs.tib.eu/wp/dini-ag-blog/2021/05/27/re3data-literaturanalyse/>

⁵⁷ Vierkant et al. (2018) and Pampel et al. (2013)

⁵⁸ Pampel et al. (2015); For a more detailed description of the icons' meanings, see the FAQs at

<https://www.re3data.org/faq>

⁵⁹ <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/>

⁶⁰ <https://fairsharing.org/>

⁶¹ Sansone et al. (2019)

⁶² <https://repositoryfinder.datacite.org/>: It is a pilot project of the Enabling FAIR Data Project led by the American Geophysical Union (AGU) in partnership with DataCite and the Earth, space and environment sciences community.

⁶³ DataCite is a global provider of DOIs for research data.

⁶⁴ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>

⁶⁵ Vierkant (2022)

⁶⁶ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

⁶⁷ <https://www.worlddatasystem.org>

(Data Seal of Approval). DSA is a certification body for repositories, which in 2018 together with the ICSU World Data System (WDS) was merged into CoreTrustSeal (CTS).

- The Federal Ministry for Education, Science and Research in Austria (abbr. BMBWF) provides a search interface on its research infrastructure website, where one can search for data repositories in Austria⁶⁸, with the option to display the search results as a map.

Table 2: Selected examples of RDR (taken from the re3data.org directory of RDR)

re3data record	About	Content focus
re3data.org: Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) ; editing status 2021-09-02; re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. http://doi.org/10.17616/R3J88J	CRAN is a network of ftp and web servers around the world that store identical, up-to-date, versions of code and documentation for R	Statistical computing
re3data.org: AUSSDA Dataverse; editing status 2021-11-25; re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. http://doi.org/10.17616/R39G72	data archive for the social science community in Austria and offers a variety of research support services, primarily data archiving and help with data re-use ⁶⁹	Social sciences
re3data.org: DARIAH-DE Repository; editing status 2020-11-26; re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. http://doi.org/10.17616/R30G8N	digital long-term archive for human and cultural-scientific research data	Digital humanities
re3data.org: RADAR ; editing status 2021-03-18; re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. http://doi.org/10.17616/R3ZX96	RDR for archiving and publishing research data from completed scientific studies and projects, focusing on data from subjects that do not yet have their own discipline-specific infrastructures for research data management	Cross-disciplinary
re3data.org: DRYAD ; editing status 2021-09-03; re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. http://doi.org/10.17616/R34S33	All material is associated with a scholarly publication	General-purpose

For researchers, intending either to deposit data or search for reusable data, access is an important feature. Concerning the different types of access, for example, the *re3data* directory groups repositories into four different levels⁷⁰:

- *open*: There are no access barriers. Both the data and their respective metadata are accessible
- *embargoed*: External users cannot overcome access barriers until the data is released and openly accessible. This refers only to the data itself.
- *restricted*: External users can overcome access barriers. Metadata can be accessed, but not the related data set.
- *closed*: External users cannot overcome access barriers. Restrictions refers to both metadata and the data itself.

⁶⁸ <https://forschungsinfrastruktur.bmbwf.gv.at/en>

⁶⁹ <https://aussda.at/en/>

⁷⁰ How open are repositories in re3data? <https://coref.project.re3data.org/blog/how-open-are-repositories-in-re3data> (6th Dec. 2021)

Restrictions may include requiring fees, registration or institutional membership. If one has identified one or more candidate RDR for deposit, it is recommended looking at their homepages for specific deposit conditions (policies or the General Terms and Conditions) and for detailed information on the deposit process. This is important in so far that a data deposit to a data archive with a highly professional data curating process (including a moderated deposit process, like AUSSDA or ICSPR) may take more time and cost than simply uploading your data files to, for example, Zenodo. On the other hand, these larger disciplinary data archives usually comply with data policies provided by funders and publishers. Furthermore, they often are approved by special repository certification organizations, hence guaranteeing high quality standards.

4. Publishers' data (sharing) recommendations and policies

In recent years, in the scholarly publication landscape, journal publishers have started developing (data) policies around the sharing or publication of research data underlying the manuscripts they are publishing. Some publishers or journals also refer authors to different data repositories in their policies or guidelines, or recommend searching a directory of data repositories (see section 3 in this chapter) - such as re3data - to find a suitable data archive for the relevant research data⁷¹. As this may be important to the authors submitting their publication, it is worth looking at some journal data policies here. For example, Springer Nature developed a framework for the research data policies of all its journals⁷². The Data policy standardisation and implementation Interest Group (IG) of the Research Data Alliance further developed this framework around existing scholarly publishers' research data policies of Springer Nature, Elsevier, Wiley, and PLOS⁷³. An overview of the research data policies of universities and other research institutions is omitted here, as it would go beyond the scope of this chapter. Also research data policies provided by public funders (e.g. Austrian Science Fund⁷⁴, ERC⁷⁵, NSF⁷⁶ or ESRC⁷⁷) will not be discussed here in detail. For an example, the reader is referred to a comparison on requirements of the Austrian Science Fund and the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme⁷⁸. In the summary section, there are a few noteworthy tips for the repository selection decision considering funding agency guidelines. Journal publisher's data policies are probably the most relevant for researchers in everyday scholarly life. Therefore, some key elements and characteristics of these policies are summarized below. However, the reader should bear in mind that this only represents a cut-out and does not reflect the entire scientific journal publisher universe. In Table 3, four prominent

⁷¹ See for example, <https://authorservices.taylorandfrancis.com/data-sharing/share-your-data/repositories/>

⁷² Hrynaszkiewicz et al. (2017)

⁷³ Hrynaszkiewicz et al. (2020)

⁷⁴ see Open Access to Research Data Guidelines of the Austrian Science Fund (FWF): <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/open-access-policy/open-access-to-research-data> (accessed 2022-10-12)

⁷⁵ European Research Council: Data Guidelines and open data policy <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines> (accessed 2022-10-12)

⁷⁶ See the *National Science Foundation Proposal & Award Policies & Procedures Guide*: https://www.nsf.gov/pubs/policydocs/pappg22_1/ (accessed 2022-10-12)

⁷⁷ see the Economic and Social Research Council's research data policy: <https://www.ukri.org/publications/esrc-research-data-policy/> (accessed 2022-10-12)

⁷⁸ Spichtinger and Blumesberger (2020)

scholarly publishers and their research data guidelines (or policies) are exemplified in condensed manner.

Table 3: A condensed summary of the policy framework spectrum of four large publishers

Publisher	Weakest (all features encouraged)	Strongest (all features required)
Wiley ⁷⁹	• DAS*	• DAS • Peer review of data
Taylor & Francis ⁸⁰	• DAS	• DAS • PID for data • Data citation
Elsevier ⁸¹	• Data deposit in a relevant data repository • Citing this dataset in the article	←————→	• Data deposit • Data citation and linking (or a DAS) • Peer review of data prior to publication
Springer ⁸²	• Data sharing • Data citation	• Data sharing • Evidence of data sharing • Peer review of data

Note: *DAS = Data Availability Statement/Data Access Statement; PID = Permanent Identifier (e.g. DOI)

There may be differences in the detailed wording and expressions in some way, but their policy frameworks show common core features:

- It provides a *general framework* – whose spectrum ranges from encouraging recommendations to strictly mandatory data (sharing) policies.
- It provides a set of data policies focusing on different groups of journals. The features within a certain type of policy range from a simply recommending to a highly encouraging character to absolute mandatory features.
- It may depend also on the journal editors/editorial board what type of policy is implemented at the journal level. Hence, the respective journal author guidelines should be read (see, for example *Nature's* editorial and publishing policies⁸³).
- The "*Data Availability Statement*" (DAS) is the feature most often provided as mandatory instrument. It is a statement about where data supporting the results reported in a published article can be found. It may contain links (e.g. a DOI) to publicly archived datasets.
- *Data journals*⁸⁴ that specialize in publishing (research) datasets (so-called data papers⁸⁵), are amongst those with the most rigid data policies. As datasets itself are the main subject of the publication, these journals require a peer review of the data. The data must be made available to editors and referees at the time of submission.

⁷⁹ John Wiley & Sons Inc. (2022)

⁸⁰ Taylor & Francis (2018)

⁸¹ Elsevier (2022a, 2022b)

⁸² Springer Nature (n.d.)

⁸³ <https://www.nature.com/palcomms/journal-policies/editorial-and-publishing-policies>

⁸⁴ Candela et al. (2015)

⁸⁵ for a detailed description of this type of journal articles see, for example, Chavan and Penev (2011)

For more details on the scope and design of the policies summarized in Table 3, see the respective pages at the publishers' websites. Two further examples of data sharing policies are those by SAGE⁸⁶ and PLOS⁸⁷. Other journals like those published by the American Economic Association (AEA) have a so-called data editor⁸⁸ who defines and monitors the journals approach to data and reproducibility. Similarly, INFORMS's⁸⁹ Management Science Journal⁹⁰ has a data editor installed, and adopted some of the data policy features from the AEA. In general, it is strongly recommended to take a close look at editorial guidelines, author guidelines and – if explicitly mentioned – a journal's data policy (sometimes termed data disclosure policy) before submitting the paper. In case of ambiguity, one should contact the journal editor or any data editor in advance.

5. Summary

Within research projects or multi-authored research articles that include or generate research data, questions about which data policies may apply, whether and where to archive which data are very important and should be addressed at the earliest possible point of time – at its best at beginning of such a research endeavor. As mentioned in the previous section, the publisher's or funder's guidelines may include specific requirements regarding the provision or archiving of research data (e.g. open data by default, certified repository, etc.). Even if there are no legal or contractual requirements regarding data archiving, there are a number of issues that should always be considered when selecting a suitable data repository.

Only recently, in the United States, a set of desirable characteristics of online, public access data repositories have been formulated to help ensure that research data are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (i.e. FAIR-principles⁹¹) to the greatest extent possible, while integrating privacy, security, and other protections.

⁸⁶ <https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/eur/research-data-sharing-policies>

⁸⁷ <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/data-availability>

⁸⁸ see <https://aeadataeditor.github.io/> and American Economic Association (2019)

⁸⁹ The Institute for Operations Research and the Management Sciences is an internationally recognized association for professionals in operations research, analytics, management science, economics, and many other related fields.

⁹⁰ <https://pubsonline.informs.org/page/mnsc/datapolicy>

⁹¹ For details see <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> or Wilkinson et al. (2016)

Table 4. Desirable Characteristics of repositories for managing and sharing data from federally funded or supported research⁹²

<i>Organizational infrastructure</i>	<i>Digital Object Management</i>	<i>Technological issues</i>	<i>Human Data related considerations</i> ⁹³
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free and easy access • Clear use guidance • Risk management • Retention policy • Long-term organizational sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unique persistent identifiers • Metadata • Curation and Quality assurance • Broad and Measured reuse • Common formats • Provenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentication • Long-term technical sustainability • Security and Integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fidelity to consent • Security • Limited use compliant • Download control • Request review • Plan for breach • Accountability

Usually it is preferable to use a *domain-specific* or *disciplinary* repository, or alternatively an *institutional* data repository. If neither of these is available, a *generalist* repository may be an option (see Section 2 above). There are some key issues to consider when depositing research data⁹⁴ and there are different options of where and how data can be archived, published and disseminated. The choice may depend on the project, the nature and *characteristic of dataset* itself, the kind of access control needed for the data, the length of preservation desired, and cost associated with publishing data and many other factors.

Table 5. Data related characteristics⁹⁵

Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hosting of common file formats (e.g. csv, xlsx, doc, pdf, etc.) • Hosting of proprietary file formats (e.g. raw image files)
Data size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limits to size per file or to total dataset size • <i>Small/medium</i> datasets (e.g. spreadsheets): datasets may be uploaded by the researcher, or transferred through university network drives to a server or the cloud, and/or uploaded by a data archivist into a repository. • <i>Medium-to-Large</i> datasets (i.e. requiring terabyte/petabyte drives): there is a larger weight toward data curation, adding robust metadata for access points and considering logical divisions of datasets/ fields in consultation with researchers • <i>Very-large</i> datasets may require consortial services or national data preservation and archiving infrastructure. At this level, the storage costs and cost for data curation may become an important issue.
Data licensing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Types of licenses available (CC0, waiver; software license, etc.) • Take care in advance, if data are licensed (e.g. from a third-party, like a commercial data-provider)
Data attribution and citation tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assignment of dataset DOIs, PIDs • references to related publications
User access controls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tiered access (e.g. administrator-level, collaborator-level, curator-level) • Journal-integrated, anonymous access (for peer review pre-publication) • Optional embargo to data release following publication
Data Access Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive data and metadata search tools • Data access via direct download

⁹² For a detailed description of the features, see The National Science and Technology Council (2022), p. 4-6.

⁹³ Very important to human data protection (see the Western-Copernicus Group Institutional Review Board (2021) White paper WCG Anonymous versus de-identified data

⁹⁴ Haaker and Corti (2020), p. 301

⁹⁵ Uzwyshyn (2016), p.21

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data downloading via API • Built-in tools for reading proprietary file formats • Integrated data analysis tools
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While there are many important issues to consider when choosing a repository or archive for depositing the data, some of these features may be more relevant in the ongoing research project, and others may be important at the end of the project when research data should be archived for the long term. Therefore, in the following table a list of some important questions is presented. These questions should be considered at the beginning of the project. However, some of these questions may not be answered in advance, but only later in the course of the project.

Table 6. Important questions regarding the choice of a research data repository

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who operates the repository? A major publicly funded organization may be a safer choice than a commercial provider, particularly where <i>long-term availability</i> is concerned. Is this archive well <i>recognized</i> within the respective research field? • How does the <i>collection policy</i> of the archive look like, i.e. what data do they collect? • What <i>legal requirements</i> (data protection, location of the repository, etc.) need to be taken into account? What GDPR rules apply? • Are the research data or parts thereof subject to <i>special restrictions</i> (e.g. requirement of de-identification, copyright protection)? • What recommendations or <i>data policies</i> are provided by the journals where the research output is supposed to be submitted? • What specifications regarding the provision of the research data are required by a <i>funder's policy</i> (e.g. is there an open data mandate; what type of repositories are recommended)? • Is there a suitable choice of different <i>licensing models</i> defining how data can be reused • Does the repository <i>enable collaborative work</i> with the data? This may be of interest during the project, especially in projects with researchers from different institutions (e.g. access to data; versioning of data sets). • Do <i>charges</i> apply for data storage? What does the funder's policy say about cost coverage (e.g. the SNSF does not cover cost for data deposits if the repository is commercial⁹⁶) • Do you need a <i>trustworthy data infrastructure</i>; is the data archive certified (e.g. CoreTrustSeal) • Is there a good search facility and is it easy to cite the data (e.g. for data reuse), for instance through the assignment of <i>persistent identifiers</i>? What about versioning of data sets (especially during a project)? • Does the repository provide appropriate <i>metadata</i> schemes for data description?

⁹⁶ Swiss National Science Foundation (2022), p. 15

Without claiming to be exhaustive, the above questions offer some first clues for the selection of a data repository. There exist quite a few tools, provided either by a special interest group in the respective research community, or by a university's research support office. For example, in 2018, the AGU Enabling FAIR Data project's Repository Guidance Targeted Adoption Group developed a detailed “*decision tree*” for researchers in the earth, space and environmental sciences⁹⁷, as a tool to determining an appropriate repository in which to deposit their data. The tree is applicable to most domains of research, funding scenarios and project stages (i.e., proposal vs. project completion), and considers many of the above listed issues with which the researcher may need to comply. If neither a domain-specific repository nor an institutional repository is a solution or neither being available, a “*generalist repository comparison*” chart⁹⁸ may assist researchers in finding a generalist repository. Such a comparison chart may be a first starting point as they provide some basic feature information like for example, size limits for data, supported metadata standards, versioning support, potential costs, etc.

Finally, for those not having already some candidate repositories in mind, it is recommended to visit some of the most comprehensive sources for data repositories and archives: the *re3data registry*⁹⁹. It has not only search capabilities, but also allows filtering and browsing for data repositories along several indicators, like for example, contenting type, country, subject and many others. A further important source is *FAIRsharing*¹⁰⁰, a community driven portal that also provides repository search, but also has a searchable database on standards and policies.

If one is still unsure what repository or data archive may fit well, it is highly recommended to contact the institution's research service support or the research data management office, respectively.

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⁹⁷ Enabling FAIR Data Community et al. (2018); see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1475430>

⁹⁸ Stall et al. (2020), see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3946719>

⁹⁹ re3data.org (2023); see <https://www.re3data.org>

¹⁰⁰ Sansone et al. (2019); see <https://fairsharing.org/>

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